

Studies on Cyclisation of Allylacetacetanilides and Spectral Characterisation of the Products

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Ring-closure of some α -(γ -substituted-allyl)acetoacetanilides has been studied. Ir and pmr spectra have been used to distinguish between the furoquinolines and pyranoquinolines obtained. Pmr spectra of some 2-substituted 2,3-dihydro-4-methylfuro[2,3-*b*]quinolines (**2**) and 2-substituted 3,4-dihydro-5-methyl-2*H*-pyrano[2,3-*b*]quinolines (**4**) are reported. The dihydropyrano[2,3-*b*]quinolines are found to have three characteristic ir absorptions of diagnostic value. Orthophosphoric acid (OPA) appears to be superior to the widely used PPA or sulphuric acid as the cyclising agent for acetoacetanilides.

Cyclisation of α -allylacetacetanilide (**1a**) to 2,3-dihydro-2,4-dimethylfuro[2,3-*b*]quinoline (**2a**) was reported by Raman¹, who established the structure from uv and ir spectral studies. This structure for the cyclisation product has been supported by later workers^{2,3} as well. The hydroxyquinoline (**3**) has been proposed as a probable intermediate in this reaction, the hydroxyl group of which adds on to the double bond of the allyl side-chain in accordance with Markovnikov's rule to afford **2a**. Several α -allylacetacetanilides have been cyclised to dihydromethylfuro[2,3-*b*]quinolines⁴ by this method. Methods for synthesis of pyranoquinolines are meagre. No reports are available on the synthesis of pyranoquinolines starting from allylacetacetanilides.

	R	R'
a;	H	H
b;	H	CH ₃
c;	H	C ₆ H ₅
d;	H	COOCH ₃
e;	CH ₃	CH ₃
f;	CH ₃	(CH ₂) ₂ CH=C(CH ₃) ₂

In the present work the ring-closures of some α -(γ -substituted-allyl)acetoacetanilides (**1**) were studied. Either a furo[2,3-*b*]quinoline or the isomeric pyrano[2,3-*b*]quinoline might result from such ring-closures and the regiochemistry of the cyclisation could be influenced by the substituent group in the γ -position of the allyl chain. Compound **1** was prepared by the PTC alkylation⁵ of acetoacetanilide with the appropriate allyl halides in presence of BTEAC as catalyst.

Alkylation of acetoacetanilide with 1-bromobut-2-ene gave the crude α -(but-2-enyl)acetoacetanilide

(**1b**) as a viscous liquid. It was cyclised as such using PPA to give a product which was resolved into two fractions on tlc. The two components **A** and **B** were separated in almost equal amounts by column chromatography. Theoretically, the cyclisation of **1b** could yield either 2,3-dihydro-2-ethyl-4-methylfuro[2,3-*b*]quinoline (**2b**) or the isomeric 3,4-dihydro-2,5-dimethyl-2*H*-pyrano[2,3-*b*]quinoline (**4b**). Elemental analysis of the bases, **A** and **B** gave identical values which were in conformity with the structures **2b** or **4b**. Ir spectrum of **A** showed the characteristic dihydrofuroquinoline band⁶ at 1 630 cm⁻¹ and the spectrum was closely similar to that of **2a**. The pmr spectra of 2-substituted 2,3-dihydro-4-methylfuro[2,3-*b*]quinolines (**2**) and 2-substituted-

3,4-dihydro-5-methyl-2*H*-pyrano[2,3-*b*]quinolines(**4**) have not been reported. Hence **2a** was chosen as a model compound and its pmr spectrum

(2)

	R
a;	CH ₃
b;	C ₂ H ₅
c;	CH ₂ -C ₆ H ₅
d;	CH(CH ₃) ₂

(a)

(4)

	R	R'
a;	H	H
b;	H	CH ₃
c;	H	C ₆ H ₅
d;	CH ₃	CH ₃

was found to exhibit signals at δ 2.53 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 1.55 (3H, d, 2-CH₃), 5.0 (1H, m, H-2), 2.9, 3.4 (1H each, dd, *J* 15 and 7 Hz, CH₂-3 non-equivalent), 7.1-7.92 (4H, m, ArH). The pmr spectrum of **A** showed signals at δ 2.53 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 1.12 (3H, t, CH₃ of 2-CH₂CH₃), 1.8 (2H, m, CH₂ of 2-CH₂CH₃), 4.85 (1H, m, H-2), 2.96, 3.35 (1H each, dd, *J* 15 and 7 Hz, CH₂-3 non-equivalent), 7.2-7.93 (4H, m, ArH), in good agreement with the furoquinoline structure **2b**. The alternate pyranoquinoline structure **4b** could be readily ruled out because of the absence of a methyl doublet representing 2-CH₃.

(3)

The ir spectrum of **B** showed no absorptions in the region 1639-1626 cm⁻¹ thereby excluding a furoquinoline structure, but exhibited three prominent bands at 1605, 1560 and 1490 cm⁻¹. An ir band at 1605 cm⁻¹ has been reported³ for **4a** but the other two bands remain unexplained. In this situation **4a** was synthesised by the method of Ramakrishnan and Shanmugam³ and reinvestigation of its ir spectrum revealed the presence of the three intense bands at 1605, 1560 and 1490 cm⁻¹ of which only the first

one has been reported by earlier workers. The pmr spectrum of **B** (vide experimental) confirmed the structure **4b**.

Cyclisation of **1b** using sulphuric acid gave a homogeneous product which was found to be identical with **B** by m.m.p., co-tlc, elemental analysis and superimposition of their ir and pmr spectra.

Thus **1b** provides a mixture of **2b** and **4b** on PPA cyclisation, whereas exclusively **4b** on H₂SO₄ cyclisation. It was observed that the presence of benzoyl peroxide or hydroquinone has no effect on the course of the cyclisation.

Alkylation of acetoacetanilide with 3-bromo-1-phenylpropene gave α -(3-phenylprop-2-enyl)-acetoacetanilide (**1c**). Attempted cyclisation of **1c** with H₂SO₄ was unsuccessful, and with PPA tarry intractable products resulted. In this context it was found that orthophosphoric acid (OPA) is an excellent reagent for cyclisation of acetoacetanilide to 1,2-dihydro-4-methyl-2-oxoquinoline and **1a** to **2a** in a yield much higher than that reported^{1,7} when H₂SO₄ or PPA is employed. Cyclisation of **1c** using OPA gave a colourless crystalline base in moderate yields. Ir spectrum of the product revealed the absence of characteristic dihydrofuroquinoline absorption in the region of 1639-1626 cm⁻¹ while the bands at 1605, 1560 and 1490 cm⁻¹ were suggestive of the pyranoquinoline (**4c**). The pmr spectrum (vide experimental) showed the absence of a methylene doublet representing the benzylic protons or protons at position-3 thereby excluding **2c** but in support of **4c**.

α -(Cyclohex-2-enyl)acetoacetanilide (**5**) which might be considered as an α -(α,γ -disubstituted allyl)acetoacetanilide was prepared from acetoacetanilide and 3-bromocyclohexene. Cyclisation of **5** using H_2SO_4 was not successful, but with

PPA or OPA a pale brown viscous liquid product was obtained. Attempted purification of the base through preparation of the hydrochloride or picrate and subsequent regeneration could not afford a solid product. Tlc revealed it to contain two fractions which were separated by column chromatography. The dominant fraction formed colourless crystals and exhibited in its ir spectrum a band at 1628 cm^{-1} indicating the furoquinoline structure (**6**). Elemental analysis and pmr spectrum (*vide experimental*) are in full agreement with this. The minor fraction, a colourless viscous liquid, exhibited no ir absorption in the region $1639\text{--}1626\text{ cm}^{-1}$ but the three bands at 1605 , 1560 and 1490 cm^{-1} were present. So it might be the pyranoquinoline (**7**). The pmr spectrum could not be studied in this case as the quantity available was insufficient.

α -(3-Carbomethoxyprop-2-enyl)acetoacetanilide (**1d**), made from acetoacetanilide and methyl γ -bromocrotonate, on treatment with H_2SO_4 or PPA could not afford any isolable product.

α -(3-Methylbut-2-enyl)acetoacetanilide (**1e**), obtained by alkylation of acetoacetanilide with 1-bromo-3-methylbut-2-ene was cyclised using OPA to give a crystalline base. Its ir spectrum showed three characteristic bands at 1605 , 1560 and 1490 cm^{-1} suggesting the pyranoquinoline structure

(**4d**) which is amply supported by the pmr signals at δ 1.43 (6H, s, 2-*gem*(CH_3)₂), 1.9 (2H, t, CH_2 -3), 2.53 (3H, s, Ar- CH_3), 2.9 (2H, t, CH_2 -4), 7.2–7.95 (4H, m, ArH). The absence of a doublet representing the methyl protons of the 2- $CH(CH_3)_2$ and the two multiplets representing the two methine protons (H-2 and H_a) and also the absence of ir absorptions in the region $1639\text{--}1626\text{ cm}^{-1}$, rules out the furoquinoline structure (**2d**) for the product. Cyclisation of **1e** using PPA or H_2SO_4 gave identical results.

α -(Geranyl)acetoacetanilide (**1f**), yet another α -(γ,γ -disubstituted-allyl)acetoacetanilide, made from acetoacetanilide and geranyl bromide, on treatment with H_2SO_4 , PPA as well as OPA, gave no isolable basic product.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) on a Hitachi R-600 FT spectrometer (60 MHz) using TMS as internal standard. Tlc was performed on silica gel G using benzene-acetone (9 : 1) as developing solvent and visualised in iodine vapour. Column chromatography was carried out over a column of silica gel using benzene-acetone (9 : 1) as eluent.

α -(But-2-enyl)acetoacetanilide (**1b**) : A solution of 1-bromobut-2-ene (4.5 g) in dichloromethane (10 ml) was added dropwise during 30 min to a stirred mixture of acetoacetanilide (5.9 g), BTEAC (1 g), dichloromethane (40 ml) and a solution of sodium hydroxide (1.4 g) in water (2.8 ml), maintained at $0\text{--}5^\circ$ in an ice-bath. The stirring was continued with cooling for 4 h more. The organic layer was then separated, washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent by distillation on a water-bath gave **1b** as a pale brown viscous liquid (7.8 g) which could not be induced to crystallise.

PPA cyclisation of **1b** to 2,3-dihydro-2-ethyl-4-methylfuro[2,3-b]quinoline (**2b**) and 3,4-dihydro-

2,5-dimethyl-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]quinoline (4b) : The crude **1b** (2.7 g) was heated with PPA (from 10 g of P₂O₅ and 6 ml of OPA) for 15 h under a CaCl₂ guard tube on a steam-bath. It was then cooled, poured into ice-water (100 ml), filtered and the filtrate basified with ammonia. The precipitated base was redissolved in HCl (5%; 60 ml), filtered and reprecipitated by ammonia to give a colourless solid (1.5 g) which was crystallised from alcohol (20%) as needles, m.p. 123°; tlc : two spots, R_f 0.7 and 0.5. Its solution (0.5 g) in benzene (4 ml) on column chromatography gave (i) **A (2b)**, 0.24 g as colourless crystals, m.p. 127–28°, tlc pure (R_f 0.7) (Found : C, 78.76; H, 7.1; N, 6.54. C₁₄H₁₅NO requires : C, 78.82; H, 7.09; N, 6.56%); ν_{\max} 1 630 cm⁻¹; picrate, needles from ethanol, m.p. 185–86°; (ii) **B (4b)**, 0.23 g as colourless crystals, m.p. 146°; tlc pure (R_f 0.5) (Found : C, 78.71; H, 7.16; N, 6.52. C₁₄H₁₅NO requires : C, 78.82; H, 7.09; N, 6.56%); ν_{\max} 1 605, 1 560 and 1 490 cm⁻¹; δ 1.54 (3H, d, 2-CH₃), 2.1 (2H, m, CH₂-3), 2.53 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.9 (2H, m, CH₂-4), 4.4 (1H, m, H-2), 7.23–8.0 (4H, m, ArH); picrate, needles from ethanol, m.p. 225–26°.

H₂SO₄ cyclisation of 1b to 4b : The crude **1b** (1 g) was mixed with pre-cooled H₂SO₄ (10 ml). The mixture was left overnight at room temperature and then heated on a steam-bath for 30 min under a CaCl₂ guard tube. After cooling, the mixture was poured into ice-water, filtered and the clear filtrate was basified with ammonia. The precipitated base was redissolved in HCl (5%; 20 ml), filtered, reprecipitated by ammonia to give **4b** (0.4 g) which was recrystallised from alcohol (20%) as colourless crystals, m.p. 146°; tlc pure (R_f 0.5) (Found : C, 78.8; H, 7.13; N, 6.62. C₁₄H₁₅NO requires : C, 78.82; H, 7.09; N, 6.56%); ν_{\max} and δ same as for **B (4b)** above; picrate, crystallised as needles from ethanol, m.p. 225–26°.

α -(3-Phenylprop-2-enyl)acetoacetanilide (1c) : Alkylation of acetoacetanilide (5.9 g) using 3-bromo-1-phenylpropene (6.6 g) by the method

described for **1b** gave **1c** (8 g, 82%) which was crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless needles, m.p. 125° (Found : C, 77.73; H, 6.48; N, 4.67. C₁₉H₁₉NO₂ requires : C, 77.77; H, 6.53; N, 4.77%); ν_{\max} 1 716 (CO), 1 639 (CONH) and 967 cm⁻¹ (*trans*-CH=CH).

3,4-Dihydro-5-methyl-2-phenyl-2H-pyrano[2,3-b]-quinoline (4c) : **1c** (6 g) was heated with OPA (88–93%; 60 ml) for 15 h under a CaCl₂ guard tube on a steam-bath. The mixture was then cooled, added to ice-water (200 ml), filtered and the clear filtrate was basified with ammonia. The precipitate was redissolved in HCl (5%; 50 ml), filtered and reprecipitated by ammonia to give **4c** (1.2 g, 21.3%) which was crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless needles, m.p. 170–71°; tlc pure (Found : C, 82.78; H, 6.23; N, 5.14. C₁₉H₁₇NO requires : C, 82.86; H, 6.22; N, 5.08%); ν_{\max} 1 605, 1 560 and 1 490 cm⁻¹; δ 2.25 (2H, m, CH₂-3), 2.48 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.9 (2H, t, CH₂-4), 5.3 (1H, dd, H-2), 7.2–8.0 (9H, m, ArH); picrate, crystallised as golden yellow spangles from ethanol, m.p. 210–11°.

OPA cyclisation of acetoacetanilide to 1,2-dihydro-4-methyl-2-oxoquinoline : Acetoacetanilide (4 g) was heated with OPA (88–93%; 40 ml) for 15 h under a CaCl₂ guard tube on a steam-bath, then cooled and poured into ice-water (200 ml) to give 1,2-dihydro-4-methyl-2-oxoquinoline (3.3 g, 92%), m.p. 223°, undepressed on mixing with an authentic sample⁷.

OPA cyclisation of 1a to 2a : Cyclisation of **1a** (1 g) by heating with OPA (10 ml) and workup of the reaction mixture as under **4c** gave **2a** (0.85 g, 92.7%), m.p. 119–20°, undepressed on mixing with an authentic sample¹.

α -(Cyclohex-2-enyl)acetoacetanilide (5) : Alkylation of acetoacetanilide (5.9 g) with 3-bromocyclohexene (5.4 g) by the method given for

1b afforded **5** (7.7 g, 89.9%) which was crystallised from alcohol (40%) as colourless needles, m.p. 145° (Found : C, 74.52; H, 7.39; N, 5.42. C₁₆H₁₉NO₂ requires : C, 74.66; H, 7.44; N, 5.44%); ν_{\max} 1 714 (CO), 1 643 (CONH) and 690 cm⁻¹ (*cis*-CH=CH).

Cyclisation of 5 to 6 and 7 : **5** (4 g) was heated with OPA (88–93%; 40 ml) for 15 h under a CaCl₂ guard tube on a steam-bath. The mixture was then cooled, poured into ice-water (150 ml), filtered and the filtrate basified with ammonia. The resulting oily liquid was extracted with ether, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the ether removed to give a pale brown oily liquid (3 g, 80.6%) which could not be induced to crystallise; tlc, two spots.

The above product (2 g) was column chromatographed to give two fractions. The dominant fraction, **6** (0.8 g) was a colourless solid which was crystallised from petroleum ether as needles, m.p. 95°, tlc pure (Found : C, 80.34; H, 7.09 ; N, 5.90. C₁₆H₁₇NO requires : C, 80.28; H, 7.16; N, 5.85%); ν_{\max} 1 628 cm⁻¹; δ 1.6 (8H, m, cyclohexane ring), 2.5 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 3.2 (1H, m, H-3), 4.65 (1H, m, H-2), 7.2–7.93 (4H, m, ArH); picrate, yellow needles (ethanol), m.p. 196–97°. The minor fraction, **7** (80 mg) was a colourless viscous liquid, tlc pure; ν_{\max} 1 605, 1 560 and 1 490 cm⁻¹; picrate, yellow needles (ethanol), m.p. 222–23°.

α -(3-Methylbut-2-enyl)acetoacetanilide (**1e**) : Alkylation of acetoacetanilide (5.9 g) with 1-bromo-3-methylbut-2-ene (5 g) by the method described for **1b** gave **1e** (7.3 g) as a pale brown viscous liquid which could not be induced to crystallise.

3,4-Dihydro-2,2,5-trimethyl-2H-pyranof[2,3-b]quinoline (**4d**) : The crude **1e** (3.5 g) was heated

with OPA (88–93%; 35 ml) for 10 h under a CaCl₂ guard tube on a steam-bath. The mixture was then cooled, poured into ice-water (200 ml), filtered and the filtrate basified with ammonia. The resulting pale brown heavy liquid was extracted with chloroform, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the chloroform removed by distillation. The residue was dissolved in HCl (5%; 50 ml), filtered and the filtrate on basification by ammonia gave **4d** (1.3 g, 35.8%) which was crystallised from petroleum ether as colourless crystals, m.p. 84°, tlc pure (Found : C, 79.36; H, 7.44; N, 6.12. C₁₅H₁₇NO requires : C, 79.24; H, 7.54; N, 6.16%); ν_{\max} 1 605, 1 560 and 1 490 cm⁻¹, picrate, crystallised as yellow needles (ethanol), m.p. 225–26°.

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